

IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF METROLOGICAL ASSURANCE OF PRODUCT QUALITY

TURSUNBOYEVA MARJONA ABDURAHMON QIZI

Jizzakh Polytechnic institute, student,

Phone number: +998937369989; tursunboyevamarjona073@gmail.com

BADALOV NOMOZ JURABOYEVICH

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, associate professor,

Phone number: +998903110662; nomozbadalov@gmail.com

Orcid: 0000-0003-3392-9150

Abstract: Metrological assurance of product quality is important, as mentioned above, product quality is a set of features that give it the ability to meet certain needs following its mission. To evaluate the quality of the product, it is necessary to evaluate the description of the specified properties, that is, it is necessary to have measurement information about the product properties.

Keywords: product, quality, standard, competition, system, standardization, metrology, quality system, regulatory document, quality management, regulation, quality indicators.

The metrological supply system is tasked with ensuring high accuracy of measurement information, creating a system and conditions for ensuring the unity of measurement in the country, providing guaranteed accuracy of the measurement information of measuring instruments, determining the terms of use, and solving all organizational, regulatory and legal issues related to the measurement problem [1].

A complex of organizational and technical measures that ensure the acquisition and use of measurement information [2]. Selection of characteristics to be assessed during measurement, testing, and control of product quality, planning of measurement, test, and control processes, development of measurement, test, and

control methods, and appropriate measurement of metrological attestation, measurement, test, and control processes provision of tools, keeping measuring tools in metrologically correct condition, performing the measurement, testing, and control processes and processing their results, training and improving the skills of specialists related to obtaining and using measurement, testing, and control results, metrological support in the enterprise is planned at a modern technical level and to determine whether it is suitable for the production of a high-quality product, it includes issues of conducting the metrological examination of the design, construction and technological documents [3].

Determination of the nomenclature of characteristics to be measured during control during the metrological examination, the introduction of optimal *necessary* accuracy of the selected characteristics, assessment of the correctness of the selection of measuring tools, and determination of the correctness of the requirements for measurement methods, ensuring the given accuracy of measurement when using unified and automated measuring tools, processing of measurement results [4]. The main issues are to determine the methods, to determine whether the units of measurement are used correctly, to analyze the product from the point of view of suitability for control, that is, to analyze whether it is possible to measure its characteristics [5]. The metrological examination allows the elimination of metrological errors at the stages of the development of construction documents and the preparation of technological processes. If these errors slip through and enter the aforementioned documents, the possibility of economic losses and losses from measurement and control errors increases [6].

Product in a market economy the role of quality [7]. The technical level and quality of the currently produced products is a characteristic features of the work of enterprises in industrially developed countries [8]. In conditions where the market is full of goods and products and competition independent of prices prevail, it is the high quality of the product that serves as the main factor of success [9]. The quality of the produced product is considered an important criterion of the activity of any

enterprise [10]. The increase in quality determines the level of survival of the firm in market conditions, the rate of scientific and technical development, the saving of all types of resources used in the enterprise, and the general increase in production efficiency [11].

An enterprise that has made significant progress in improving the quality of its products, increases the share of the sales market, increases the price of the product at the exit of the enterprise and, accordingly, the profit of the enterprise, conducts the advertising campaign of the product and the company as a whole more effectively, strengthens the trust of business partners in the implementation of mutual product deliveries, the level of competitiveness of the product increasing and strengthening the practical image of the enterprise will have real opportunities [12]. The increase in the production of high-quality products by our enterprises should eventually lead to the rapid development of the economy, the increase in the standard of living of the population, and the increase in the competitiveness of the goods of our country both in the domestic and world markets [13]. Modern enterprises need to more effectively use economic, organizational, and legal tools to influence the processes of formation, provision, and maintenance of the necessary quality level at all stages of the product life cycle [14].

Product quality management criteria. Any management system has management criteria that determine its effectiveness [15]. In our example, the quality of the product, as mentioned above, is characterized by its ability to satisfy certain needs according to its function. From the point of view of quality management, these characteristics can be considered management criteria. For example, if it is necessary to reduce the consumption of materials, the mass of the machine is taken as a criterion. If it is necessary to increase reliability, as a criterion, the car will work without stalling, etc [16].

Product quality and competitiveness The modern market economy imposes fundamentally different requirements on the quality of the manufactured product. This is because the survival of any company and its stable position in the market of goods and services is determined by its level of competitiveness. In turn, competitiveness depends on two indicators - the level of the product price and the level of quality, where

the second indicator, according to its importance, surpasses the indicators of labor productivity, saving all kinds of resources, and is gradually coming to the fore. Quality as a factor of competitiveness extends to the entire national economy [17]. It helps to use resources wisely. In addition, product quality is an important indicator of enterprise activity. Improving product quality is a common line of work for all leading companies in the world.

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